
THE SUPPOSED CURVATURE OF REALITY

Nick VAN LIEFFERINGE

Assuming that 'nothing' (**N**) is the same as 'infinite everything' (∞ **E**):

$$(\mathbf{N} = \infty \mathbf{E})$$

than 'reality' (**R**) is completely curved.

$$(\mathbf{N} = \infty \mathbf{E}) \Rightarrow \mathbf{R}$$